

Elite Healers Sports Massage is more than just a massage, it's therapy. They are setting a higher standard in the world of massage therapy. Elite Healers Sports Massage services in NYC include: Sports Massage Therapy, Medical Massage Therapy, Deep Tissue Massage Therapy, Swedish Massage Therapy, Thai Massage, and Chair Massage Office Events. They provide recovery for athletes of all levels with Sports Massage. They also help people manage chronic muscle pain, recover from injuries, recover from surgery and help to provide muscle relief to those who just have regular muscle aches and pains by providing medical massage services as well. You can book a 60, 90, or 120 minute session. Visit the Elite Healers Sports Massage website at <https://www.elitehealerssportsmassage.com> to book an appointment or to see their hours of operation.

Now that you know more about Elite Healers Sports Massage, let's talk about sports massage benefits. Whether you have an injury, are suffering from chronic pain or just want to relieve stress, deep tissue massage can help. It works to improve flexibility and circulation, break up scar tissue, release muscle tension and increase blood flow.

It also has positive effects on systolic and diastolic blood pressure readings, reduces depression, and boosts serotonin levels. It has been proven to increase the body's production of oxytocin, the hormone that helps with bonding and making you [Sports Massage NYC](#) feel happy. You should consult your doctor before you start a deep tissue massage if you have a medical condition or an existing injury that affects your muscles, joints or bones.

Pregnancy and Postpartum:

Studies have shown that women who get a massage before or during pregnancy experience a decrease in anxiety and depression. They also sleep better because of the increased serotonin and oxytocin levels, which are often associated with relaxation.

Sports Performance and Recovery:

Many athletes benefit from deep tissue massage because it breaks up scar tissue, increases range of motion, and increases elasticity in their muscles. This can help runners and other athletes recover after strenuous training sessions or intense workouts. It can also improve sports performance in people who have a chronic illness or condition, like diabetes or arthritis. In these cases, deep tissue massage can work to ease the pain and stiffness in the affected areas, which can help you get back to doing what you love most.

During a deep tissue massage, the therapist will use their fingertips, knuckles, hands, elbows and forearms to manipulate your muscles. They may also ask you to breath deeply, which promotes relaxation and reduces stress.

The massage therapist will begin by warming up your muscles with a lighter touch, then they'll focus in on the painful areas. They can then continue to adjust their pressure, as needed, to ensure that the deep tissue massage is effective.

Your therapist will ask you what level of pressure you are comfortable with and what areas you would prefer to have worked on. If you feel any pain or discomfort, let them know so they can adjust their pressure. It's important to find a massage therapist who can work with your body's pain tolerance level and is experienced in deep tissue massage techniques. If your therapist isn't experienced or doesn't have the right techniques, you won't receive any benefits from the massage.

If you're a beginner to deep tissue massage, you can get started with a Swedish massage or pressure point therapy before moving on to deeper, more intense treatments. Most therapists offer several different types of massage, so you can choose the one that best suits your needs. Now that you know more about the many benefits of sports massage, it is time to go back to the website of Elite Healers Sports Massage to schedule an appointment today!